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Toward a probabilistic theory of the measuring systems

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Toward a probabilistic theory of the measuring system

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Abstract. In the current debate on measurement science, there is growing interest in identifying some generic framework for the modelling of the measurement system. Recently, we have proposed sufficient conditions for an empirical system to qualify as a measuring system, and have proposed a deterministic framework based on that. Here we consider turning that framework into a corresponding probabilistic one, in order to properly accounting for measurement uncertainty.

1. Introduction

The notion of measurement (or measuring) system has been recently considered as a key issue in measurement science [1 – 5,8,10]¹, and essential for measurement to qualify as an autonomous discipline. The development of a general agreed view of measurement among disciplines, constituted the key focus of, e.g., the IMEKO Joint TC1-TC7-TC13 event, hold in Berkeley, in 2016 [7].

As a part of such a debate, we have formerly proposed a generic model of the measurement process, based on the primitive notion of “empirical relations”, and we have developed a formal theory for that [11], based on deterministic framework.

Here we discuss the re-formulation of that theory, in order to allow for a proper expression of measurement uncertainty. In doing so, we continue we follow the perspective of considering probability as “logic” (or, more informally, a mathematical-logical tool) for dealing with uncertainty in measurement, taking a position that aims at overcoming the current, trite in our opinion, controversial between the supporters of a frequentistic or of a Bayesian view of statistic-probabilistic discipline, which we consider a sterile and useless exercise [12].

2. Résumé of the underlying deterministic framework

The underlying deterministic framework is summarised in Figure 1.

Let us then consider an ordinal quantity x , characterised by the order structure (A, \succsim_A) , where A is a set of objects that carry the quantity x , and \succsim_A is a weak order on A . Then a measurement system for x may be modelled as a system that interacts with the objects in A , and produces outputs, as realizations, $b \in B$, of some quantity y , that we will call (instrument) indications.

¹ References are listed in a chronological order to give a sense of the evolution of the subject.

The measurement system is thus fully characterized by the structure $(A, \succ_A, B, \succ_B, \varphi)$, where \succ_B is a strict order on B , and $\varphi: A \rightarrow B$, is a monotonic function, such that, for each $a_1, a_2 \in A$,

$$a_1 \succ_A a_2 \leftrightarrow \varphi(a_1) \succ_B \varphi(a_2). \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 Illustration of the measurement process, reprinted from [11].

As shown in the Figure, when we input the object a to the measuring system we obtain the indication $b \in B$, through the function φ . If we now consider a *reference scale*, R , for the quantity x , and the restriction of φ to S , call it φ_s , if we apply to b the inverse of φ_s , φ_s^{-1} , we identify the standard $s \in S$ that would have produced the same indication that has been produced by a , and thus it make sense to assign to a the same value, $m(s)$, we obtain a proper measurement value. Therefore the entire measurement process may be properly described by the function $\gamma: A \rightarrow X$, with $X = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, defined by

$$\gamma(a) = m(\varphi_s^{-1}(\varphi(a))). \quad (2)$$

In particular, we have proved that, for each $a_1, a_2 \in A$,

$$a_1 \succ a_2 \leftrightarrow \gamma(a_1) \geq \gamma(a_2). \quad (3)$$

3. The probabilistic framework

Following the same line of thought as in Ref. [4], we have to re-interpret the above framework under a probabilistic logic.

This implies two main step:

- Re-interpreting the representational structures associated to the input, x , and output, y , quantities, and
- Re-interpreting the function φ , and all subsequent transformations, related to it.

The re-interpretation of the relational structure associated to the measurand, x , requires the introduction of the notion of a probabilistic relational structure, that basically consists in a (finite) collection of such structures, with an associated probability distribution. This allows to, for each $a_1, a_2 \in A$, to assign a well-defined meaning to the statement $P(a_1 \succcurlyeq a_2)$. With this approach, we attain at the probabilistic formulation of the representational theorem, that, for ordinal quantities, reads

$$P(a_1 \succcurlyeq a_2) = P[m(a_1) \geq m(a_2)]. \quad (4)$$

Concerning the indication, instead, we may still consider a deterministic structure.

Let us now consider the measurement system and the associated measurement process.

The overall transformation is described by the function γ , which is a combination of three functions, φ, φ_s and m . Whilst m , at least as a first approach, may be still considered deterministic, the other two need to be turned into probabilistic. The notion of probabilistic function has been presented in Ref. [11], and it is based on assuming a probability distribution over a finite set of structures compatible with the function under consideration. For a generic function, $f: U \rightarrow V$, this allows giving a well-defined meaning, for each $u \in U$ and $v \in V$, to the statement $P(f(u) = v)$.

This also allows to find a rule for the inversion and composition of functions.

Concerning inversion, we may prove that [6]

$$P(u = f^{-1}(v)) = P(v = f(u)) \left[\sum_w P(v = f(w)) \right]^{-1}. \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, in regard to composition, if f is the composition of g and h , we can prove that

$$P(v = f(u)) = \sum_w P(v = h(w)) P(w = g(u)). \quad (6)$$

Thanks to these rules, we can now turn Eq. (2) into a probabilistic one. Let $b = \varphi(a)$, $s = \varphi_s^{-1}(b)$, $\hat{x} = \gamma(a) = m(s)$, and, remembering that m has been assumed to be deterministic and one-to-one, $s = m^{-1}(\hat{x})$. Then we obtain

$$P(\hat{x} = \gamma(a)) = \sum_b \frac{P(b = \varphi_s(m^{-1}(\hat{x})))}{\sum_\zeta P(b = \varphi_s(\zeta))} P(b = \varphi(a)). \quad (7)$$

which constitutes the desired probabilistic counterpart of Eq. (2).

4. Conclusions

The notion of measuring system is gaining increasing interest in measurement science. Here we have considered a model of the measuring system, in terms of empirical relations among objects to be measured and the measuring device, and we have proposed a suited probabilistic counterpart of its, which allows to express in formal terms, the measurement uncertainty associated to it.

Progress in the modelling of the measurement process has an intrinsic value as an essential part of a (any) theory of measurement [4, 5, 7, 10] and has direct application counterparts, including a possible (deep) revision of the Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement, in order to better meet the expectation of people involved in measurement activities [12].

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